

Inspiring the next generation of researchers with data sharing

For Youssef Zeidan, MD, PhD, data sharing and reuse via the Vivli platform has been an essential mentoring tool that has helped launch his medical students' careers.

As a faculty member at American University of Beirut, Dr. Zeidan mentored four students conducting research into the benefits of radiation therapy as a treatment for breast cancer. Each student used the Vivli platform to access clinical trial data from Roche. These case studies demonstrate the value that data sharing platforms like Vivli can offer for new investigators and students in addition to expanding scientific knowledge.

Dataset(s) used: See Vivli data requests [5930](#), [5931](#), and [7583](#).

“Data sharing really goes a long way in the modern era. It is very impactful for generating new science, new ideas, changing guidelines, but also it is very effective in crossing borders and mentoring the next generation of researchers and scientists.”

Youssef Zeidan, MD, PhD

Watch: [Dr. Zeidan discusses his students' projects at the 2025 Vivli Annual Meeting](#)

Current position: Postdoctoral Fellow, Cleveland Clinic

Key points:

- As a medical student, Bachir led a project looking at cardiac events among patients treated with radiation therapy and trastuzumab.
- Using HERA trial data accessed via Vivli, the team found that patients getting left-side breast cancer radiation therapy had a higher incidence of cardiac events.
- However, the absolute differences between left and right side were small, suggesting that it may be possible to plan radiation therapy to reduce cardiovascular risks.

Read more: [Bachir, B., et al., *International Journal of Radiation Oncology*Biography*Physics* \(2022\)](#)

Bachir Bachir, MD

GREI data reuse story
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Current position: Resident Physician, Stanford University

Key points:

- As a medical student, Jaoude led an investigation into whether HER-2 positive breast cancer patients benefited from a radiation boost to the lumpectomy cavity.
- The research team used the Vivli platform to look at data from 1,000 participants in the HERA trial.
- They found that there was no additional benefit to adding a radiation boost.

Read more: [Jaoude, J.A., et al., *International Journal of Radiation Oncology*Biology*Physics* \(2020\).](#)

Joseph Abi Jaoude, MD

Majd Kayali, MD

Current position: Cardiology Fellow, Mercy Health–St. Vincent Medical Center

Key points:

- While in medical school, Kayali examined whether triple-negative breast cancer patients treated with systemic therapy and mastectomy also benefitted from post-mastectomy radiation therapy.
- The research team used the Vivli platform to look at data from participants in the BEATRICE trial.
- They found that very few patients benefitted from post-mastectomy radiation therapy.

Read more: [Kayali, M., et al., *Annals of Surgical Oncology* \(2021\).](#)

Current position: Assistant Professor, MD Anderson

Key points:

- As a student, Saifi examined whether node-positive breast cancer patients who become node-negative after systemic therapy benefit from radiation therapy.
- Using data from the TRYPHAENA and NeoSphere trials accessed via Vivli, the team found that only patients who were node-positive at the time of surgery benefitted from post-mastectomy radiation therapy.
- These results were cited in recent [clinical guidelines](#) for breast cancer radiation therapy.

Read more: [Saifi, O., et al., *Radiotherapy and Oncology* \(2020\).](#)

Omran Saifi, MD